

WHY NAMIBIA'S EDUCATION IS GETTING WEAKER – AND WHY LEADERSHIP STANDARDS MUST RISE

By *DR SHIHALA ELIAKIM (PHD)*

Over the past decade, Namibia has expanded education access at all levels. More children are attending school, and tertiary enrolment has grown significantly. Yet learning outcomes continue to decline. The uncomfortable truth is that quantity and access have expanded far faster than quality, equity, leadership, management, and administrative capacity.

From early childhood education to universities, there so many schools branches and Universities satellites across the country offering the same subject, the same swallow knowledge and the same theory, not only that the system faces multiple challenges. Lowered minimum entry standards mean that many teachers, lecturers, tutors, trainers, Heads of Department and principals, and even some lecturers at universities, lack advanced academic qualifications. The old fashioned Diploma-level pathways remain the minimum requirement for leadership, administration and even teaching, leaving many in positions of responsibility without the advance research knowledge or deeper pedagogical expertise needed to guide teaching and learning effectively. Whether its leaders themselves or its teachers leadership, it sets the culture for teaching and learning; without strong, qualified leaders, innovation, mentoring, and instructional quality inevitably suffer. Although research indicates that Namibia sacrifice quality with merit of experience, evidence shows that, there is a need to upgrade to the next level. HoDs should hold Master's

degrees, principals PhDs, and all education CEOs must hold PhDs with relevant experience to ensure educational excellence.

Research shows that, the burden on leaders and lecturers has grown with the expansion of schools and universities. Officers are often responsible for workloads far beyond what is reasonable, and the system has failed to provide adequate resources or support. Even when some regions perform well, most major events, workshops, and resource allocations remain concentrated in Windhoek, 700 km away. The centralisation of training and resources has left regional schools and universities under-supported, demoralised educators, and hindered local innovation. The result is a system where leaders often cannot implement policies effectively, not because of a lack of effort, but because they lack the time, resources, and expertise to do so.

Data has demonstrated that quality assurance in the education sector is another major weakness as there are no systems to keep statistics or share new information that can inform change. Many leaders operate based on ego, pride, personal agendas, or political loyalties rather than serving the public. Inspectors, advisors, and senior officers frequently work independently, ignoring policy directives as some directives do not have due dates. Cluster and circuit systems are outdated, slow to respond, and incapable of addressing emerging issues efficiently as they lack resources, they are far from the schools and they lack personnel to timely address their needs. Political interference in those regions further compounds the problem, with divisions among leaders and teachers often prioritizing political allegiance over educational merit.

Many leaders themselves need political education to understand governance, impartiality, and the importance of putting education above politics in order to serve every Namibian. Namibia is no longer a country of equals' rights, equal resources; it's a country that has divided people based on where they get their bread and not a place where leaders openly ready to serve their people. As Education is always continuously changing, Curriculum changes has no exception. However as education's needs and interest changes, those changes are not well managed, new policies are poorly implemented across the country, as educators are torn between following old directives

and adopting new ones, which hampers the reforms and improvements urgently needed. Namibia lack a uniformed system that speaks to everyone at same time, The use of televisions, radios, social media, is more ridiculed and abused, as such, our country lack a platform to share issues that truly affect the education system, at national level, the Ministry of Information and technology is doing less to uplift the spirit of sharing timely and valid information. Regional councils rarely speaks about issues that are affecting their regions, in terms of education, rather their information are too basic and more as directives. Lack of communication in those regions has fueled political divisions and inconsistent implementation practices have caused more harm than any benefit, weakening collaboration, trust, and progress across schools and regions.

Assessment and examination are the cornerstone of a quality education, yet those systems have also suffered. Officials responsible for educational works are rarely doing their work, as more and more educational assessment and projects, workshops are always delayed, late or attended only to a few, perhaps Windhoek and Okahandja has the most respected teachers who always chosen randomly to represent all the educators in the country. The removal of the Cambridge system has weakened Namibia national examinations, and leaving assessment largely in the hands of teachers and education officers increased access but not quality. Automatic promotion of learners based on age in schools has further undermines learning, leaving students advancing without mastering core skills, also weaken the distance learning option, especially Namcol has been doing well in helping learners upgrade but automation promotion, has weaken this special idea that was helping those who fail to upgrade further. Namibia urgently needs a centralized, professional University of Education to manage examinations, standardize assessments, and ensure accountability, ensuring that learner progression reflects real competencies rather than administrative convenience. Nothing strengthens education quality than the power of quality training in assessments of learning. Entry qualifications for teachers are not enough to truly uplift Namibia education. There is a need for specialists who would set exam and mark that exam rather than just part-time randomly untrained setters and moderators.

Furthermore, Corruption in teacher recruitment remains a pressing concern. Many educators had lamented about unfair appointments, yet little action is taken. A transparent, nationwide online testing and interview system could curb corruption and ensure that teacher recruitment prioritizes merit, competence, and quality, rather than personal connections or political alignment. Moreover lack of expertise in conducting interviews can also be the reason why many candidates fail and why others pass, by luck, teachers who conduct interview needed to have assessor and moderator certifications, rather than just a qualification and experience, so that they truly measure the competencies of candidates fairly. Its possible interviews that conducted by humans are prone to errors, plus a teacher who never went through interview course or assessment of competencies can rarely achieve the best result.

The silence of educators across Namibia is deeply worrying me and very troubling. Yes research has shown that teachers are highly disciplined individuals and are good and easy to work with. Teachers and lecturers shape society, influence standards of living, and impact the nation's future, yet they remain largely voiceless. Given the challenge of low salaries, poor recognition, weak union representation, and fear of authoritarian leaders have created an environment where many educators are more silent and some leave their posts rather than speak out. Even unions often benefit only a few and treat teachers as if they were children, failing to negotiate adequately for salaries or working conditions fairly. If Namibia truly values education, educators must be empowered to speak up, especially about their benefits, as teachers truly carry this country, they are needed to, participate in policy-making that benefit education, and be recognised for their expertise and commitment. Their voice is not just important, it is indispensable.

Just as a higher production of learners who are not competent is seen in Namibian schools and society, Higher education have produced more graduates who are poorly equipped for the world of work. Given the satellites branches of universities faces its own structural weaknesses. Many satellites universities across the country lack the number of PhDs who could produce such a higher number of Honours, masters and doctoral graduates. Those universities have lecturers who lack PhDs, which limits research output, postgraduate supervision, and innovation. Diploma-level minimum

entry standards at universities weaken Honours, Master's, and PhD programmes, leaving them under-resourced and fragile. Without strong undergraduate led by highly qualified postgraduate educators, Namibia cannot develop the academic expertise necessary to sustain high-quality education or produce graduates equipped for research, innovation, and leadership.

These issues are compounded by policy implementation gaps. While Namibia has adopted frameworks such as the Education Act, the Child Care and Protection Act, the Sector Policy on Inclusive Education, and commitments to international standards through UNICEF, UNESCO, and Education International, these policies are often poorly enforced. Professional development, monitoring, assessment integrity, and leadership standards remain weak, undermining the intent of these laws and frameworks.

Looking ahead, the proposed free tertiary education in 2026 is politically attractive but carries serious risks. Subsidised primary and secondary education over the past decade was a truly and applaud way, however automation promotion has not significantly improved learning outcomes. Expanding free tertiary access to universities without first addressing recruitments of qualified lecturers, leadership, quality assurance, assessment, and educator capacity risks devaluing higher education and leaving graduates unprepared for the workforce or postgraduate research. Free tertiary education must be carefully phased, as a matter of addressing poverty with disadvantaged children supported by structural reforms and sustainable investment, rather than rolled out as a political slogan that would benefits the elites. Research indicated that there is a chance for free education to saturate jobs and weaken the educational quality. .

Namibia's education system is slowly eroding under the weight of weak standards, under qualified educators and leadership, under qualified educators in secondary education and higher education, political interference, centralised resources, flawed assessment, and silenced educators and by too many satellites universities.

Truly speaking, this time is no longer about quantity and access, its about quality and equity, therefore to restore quality and equit in Namibia education system, the country must first raise minimum academic requirements to Honours degree in education and university teaching must be for PhD candidates only and competition based on publication. The minister of education must enforce quality assurance measures, accountability, decentralize resources, develop and funds systems of communications in schools and universities, strengthen assessment systems through workshops and training, curb corruption by using cameras and online testing, empower educators, and fully implement national and international policies and frameworks. Education is the backbone of national development, and without decisive reform, Namibia continue to risks producing graduates who have access but lack competence, and a system that measures numbers rather than quality. The time to act is now for the sake of learners, educators, and the nation's future.

About the Author

Dr. Shihala Eliakim holds a Doctor of Philosophy in Curriculum Studies and Instruction, a master of education in curriculum studies, Postgraduate diploma in education, Bacheror honours degree in Business adminstration. He mentor Novice teachers and He is a teacher at Omeyantalala Combined School in the Oshikoto Region and writes in his personal capacity. He can be contacted at ongwediva8@gmail.com.